

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 61.489 Max: 62.414	1407 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic	

In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No	In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No	Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 1782-8	Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No #:
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DEFINITION	Covered by ☒ SU: 0	Fills ☐ SU:	Filled by ☒ SU: 1058, 1406
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☐ Composition ☐ Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☐ Construction ☒ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
☐ Pottery ☐ Tiles ☐ Amphorae ☐ Dolia ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Mortar ☐ Coins ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Glass	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive Compaction ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft Color ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: ☒ Original ☐ Not Original
Northern Limit ☐ Original ☒ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit ☐ Original ☐ Not Original ☒ Excavation Limit	
Western Limit ☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit ☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by:	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts: 1400, 1405
Is filled by: 1406	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
 Dry, sunny conditions

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: Runs N-S along W edge of area. ends @ S. edge
 Shape: thin, long, irregular N-S rectangle

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: ☒ rounded ☐ straight Cut sides: ☒ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☒ irregular How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☒ rounded How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☒ rounded Observations: irregular width disappears near southern edge of road 1400 + reappears further north	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
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wall SU 1391
 Via Campi SU 1400
 90906

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

cut ~~1407~~ represents the trench dug for the construction of retaining wall 1058. It post-dates road 1400 as indicated by its disruption of the western-most paving blocks.
 about half-meter deep, bedrock found towards middle of cut - not found in far north and south

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by: T. Hunt (Z. Fox)

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on: